

UV spectrophotometric approach for the determination of Capmatinib in pharmaceutical dosage form: Development and validation

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Abstract

The present study used a UV spectrophotometric approach to develop and validate a new accurate, specific analytical method for determining Capmatinib in pharmaceutical dosage form. This method was developed by selecting methanol as solvent for estimating Capmatinib and detected at 254 nm. The International Conference on Harmonization guidelines were followed in the validation of the designed approach. In the 5-25 µg/ml concentration range, an excellent linear response with a correlation coefficient of 0.999 was seen. It was discovered that the limit of quantification and limit of detection was found to be 3.19 µg/ml and 1.05 µg/ml respectively. The developed procedure was also discovered to be accurate, specific, precise, and sensitive. The determination of Capmatinib in pharmaceutical dosage form for routine analysis can be accomplished with ease using this method.

Key Words

Capmatinib, UV spectrophotometry, Method development, Validation, Accurate, Sensitive.

I. INTRODUCTION

Capmatinib is an antineoplastic drug that is used for the treatment of patients with locally advanced or metastatic mesenchymal-epithelial transition (MET) exon 14 skipping (METex14) mutated non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Capmatinib is an orally bioavailable inhibitor of hepatocyte growth factor receptor (HGFR) it selectively binds to c-Met, followed by inhibiting c-Met phosphorylation and disturbing c-Met signal transduction pathways. That may lead to cell death in tumor cells overexpressing c-Met protein [1-2]. The chemical name of Capmatinib is 2-fluoro-N-methyl-4-[7-(quinolin-6-ylmethyl)imidazo[1,2-b][1,2,4]triazin-2-yl]benzamide and its molecular formula is C₂₃H₁₇FN₆O. The molar weight of Capmatinib is 412.4 g/mol [3]. Capmatinib had received its first approval on 6 May 2020 in the USA [4]. The structure of Capmatinib is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Chemical structure of Capmatinib

According to the literature review, analytical methods are based only on RP-HPLC [5-10] and LC-MS/MS [11-14] for estimating Capmatinib in drug formulations. However, it was clear that no UV spectrophotometric technique was created to estimate Capmatinib in drug formulations. Therefore, the goal of the current study was to create and verify a UV spectrophotometric technique for calculating Capmatinib in pharmaceutical formulations.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Reagents and chemicals

Capmatinib standard drug was presented as a gift sample from Simson Pharma Limited, Mumbai, India. The Taveco tablets were brought from a neighborhood drug store. All the solvents and chemicals utilized to develop this method were procured from Merck, Mumbai, India.

Instruments

The major instrument used to determine Capmatinib was a T60V UV double-beam spectrophotometer equipped with matching quartz cuvettes measuring 1 cm. All the parameters were operated using UV Win software. Along with this, bath sonicator and digital balance were also used.

Standard and sample solution preparation

A standard stock solution of 1000 µg/ml concentration was prepared using the Capmatinib standard. Later a concentration of 15 µg/ml was prepared from the above stock solution.

The average weight of 20 tablets of Taveco was determined and crushed to fine powder. An amount equivalent to 10 mg of drug was weighed and a solution of 1000 µg/ml concentration was prepared. From the above solution, 15 µg/ml solution was prepared for further measurements.

Method validation

The developed method was validated for the following parameters [15, 16]

Linearity

For the determination of linearity, serial dilutions ranging from 5-25 µg/ml were prepared from the stock solution, and respective absorbances measured. A linearity plot was made between absorbance and concentration and the correlation coefficient was determined.

Precision

The precision of the method was estimated by calculating % relative standard deviation (RSD) using inter-day and intra-day procedures. 3 µg/ml solution was prepared and measured in six replicates on the same day and after 2 days.

Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was determined based on % recovery. 50%, 100% and 150% concentration levels of drug solutions were prepared and absorbance was measured.

Specificity

The specificity of the method was determined by comparing the drug solution with a blank solution and observing the interference from solvent absorbance with Capmatinib absorbance.

Sensitivity

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) of the method were calculated based on the standard deviation and slope of the linearity curve.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The goal of the current work was to develop and validate a novel, straightforward UV spectrophotometric technique for determining the presence of Capmatinib in drug formulations

Capmatinib, the reference medication used in the creation of this approach, was first put through solubility trials in which it was made to dissolve in a variety of solvents, including methanol, acetonitrile, water, 0.1N hydrochloric acid, and 0.1N sodium hydroxide. The drug was found to be readily soluble in methanol. For this reason, methanol solvent was utilized as a diluent in the creation of solutions for additional research.

As seen in Fig. 2, a standard solution with a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was generated and scanned in a UV spectrophotometer in the 200–400 nm UV range to determine the wavelength for the measurement. The wavelength at which maximum absorbance was found to be present, 254 nm, was used to guide more research.

Fig. 2: UV spectrum of Capmatinib

The absorbance of prepared standard and sample solutions was measured and the results of optical characteristics were presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Optical Characteristics

S. No.	Parameters	Results
1	Absorption maximum	254 nm
2	Linearity Range	5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3	Regression Equation	$y = 0.0262x + 0.0055$
4	Slope	0.0262
5	Intercept	0.0055
6	Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9994
7	Molar extinction coefficient ($\text{L}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	46556
8	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ - 0.001 absorbance units)	0.0088
9	Accuracy (% recovery)	99.97 % - 100.47 %
10	Precision (Intra-day) % RSD (Inter-day) % RSD	0.27 0.19
11	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
12	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	3.19 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
13	Standard error	0.008375
14	Specificity	Specific, No interference

Absorbance was evaluated after repeated dilutions in the 5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ range were made to assess the linearity of the procedure. Subsequently, as shown in Fig. 3, a graph was drawn with concentration values on the x-axis and absorbance values on the y-axis. The outcomes were compiled in Table 2. Correlation coefficient values were calculated from the graph, and 0.9994 was the result.

Fig. 3: Linearity plot of Capmatinib

Table 2: Results of linearity

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	5	0.113
2	10	0.259
3	15	0.394
4	20	0.523
5	25	0.645
Regression coefficient (r^2)		0.9991
Correlation coefficient (r)		0.9994

The created approach was precise, as indicated by the %RSD for intra-day and inter-day precision investigations, which were determined to be 0.27 and 0.19, respectively. Tables 3a and 3b show the results for precision.

Table 3a: Intra-day precision results

Sample name	Sample absorbance	% assay
1	0.394	99.29
2	0.395	99.55
3	0.395	99.29
4	0.396	99.80
5	0.393	99.04
6	0.395	99.55
Average	0.395	99.42
% RSD	0.27	0.27

Table 3b: Inter-day precision results

Sample name	Sample absorbance	% assay
1	0.391	99.29
2	0.390	99.04
3	0.392	99.55
4	0.392	99.55
5	0.391	99.29
6	0.391	99.34
Average	0.391	99.34
% RSD	0.19	0.19

The percentage recovery was calculated to ascertain the method's accuracy. The recovery percentage was discovered to be between 99.97 and 100.47 percent, indicating the accuracy of the approach. Table 4 presents a summary of the accuracy results.

Table 4: Accuracy results

Sample No.	Level (in %)	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	50	5.00	4.99	99.80	100.47
2	50	5.00	5.01	100.30	
3	50	5.00	5.06	101.31	
1	100	10.00	9.95	99.55	99.97
2	100	10.00	10.01	100.05	
3	100	10.00	10.03	100.30	
1	150	15.00	15.02	100.14	100.30
2	150	15.00	15.05	100.30	
3	150	15.00	15.07	100.47	

When the UV-visible spectrums of the standard and blank solutions were examined, the blank solution's spectra showed no interference, suggesting that the approach was particular. Fig. 4 displays the blank spectrum.

Fig. 4: Blank Spectrum

IV. CONCLUSION

Capmatinib in pharmaceutical dosage form was determined using a novel, straightforward UV spectrophotometric approach that was developed and verified by ICH principles. The development process was discovered to be sensitive, linear, accurate, and precise. The estimation of Capmatinib for routine analysis or quality control in formulations can be accomplished with ease using this proposed method.

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Conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest

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